

Aurora Open Science Knowledge Base

Document Information

Appendix to:	Deliverable 6.2 - <i>A shared knowledge base of Open Science resources, policies and best practices</i>
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This document contains the responses on our Open Science survey from the Aurora partner universities, which were collected in May 2023. As activities/ policies/ infrastructures for Open Science at Aurora universities are rapidly progressing, this knowledge base should be seen as a snapshot in time instead of a definitive list.

The university abbreviations used in this document are:

UI - Haskoli Islands; VU - Stichting Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam; UDE - Universitaet Duisburg-Essen; URV - Universitat Rovira i Virgili; UIBK - Universitaet Innsbruck; UNINA - Universita degli studi di Napoli Federico III; UPOL - Univerzita Palackeho v Olomouci; UEA - University of East Anglia; CBS - Copenhagen Business School

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Aurora and Open Science

Within the Aurora institutions, there is a lot of momentum for Open Science. As one of the tasks in *Work Package 6: Open Science*, we set out to create a collection of the current Open Science policies, tools, solutions and practices as a valuable resource for all Aurora partners and beyond. We have structured this knowledge base according to the five requirements for Open Science described below.

Requirements for Open Science

Open Science requires a new way of working, which is driven by funders, institutional and governmental policies, technology, and, importantly, by intrinsic motivation from many researchers, teachers, students and support staff themselves. To facilitate the transition to Open Science sketched in the vision above, an academic environment should be created that meets several requirements:

- **Policy.** It is crucial that academic institutions signal their commitment to Open Science by incorporating its principles and practices (e.g. [DORA](#)) in stimulating policies, implementation, dedicated funding and support. It is essential to appreciate disciplinary differences and thus allow for different paces and priorities, while remaining adamant on the direction of change.
- **Recognition & Rewards.** In the current academic environment, practices reflecting the Open Science values—ranging from sharing results, altruistic cooperation, and engaging with stakeholders outside academic institutions—are not the norm, as they generally are not rewarded. To facilitate the transition to Open Science and, reward structures should change in such a way that its values and practices are better recognized and rewarded. To this end, concrete quantitative metrics for and qualitative evaluation of contributions (scientific output, as well as activities like leadership, mentoring, reflection and teamwork) to Open Science values and practices need to be developed.
- **Community Engagement.** To transition towards an open academic culture, it is important to create awareness of the Open Science principles and practices by facilitating a lively Open Science Community of academics and support staff. Within local Open Science Communities, members can learn from each other's experiences and share their good practices for Open Science during events, workshops and regular meetings. Next to this, engagement with society must be encouraged in order to provide for open, inclusive, and participatory processes for knowledge creation.
- **Support & Training.** Researchers, teachers, and students need to be provided with the necessary awareness, skills and knowledge they need for engaging in Open Science. This requires professionalisation of current scientific, support, and teaching staff and the emergence of new roles like data stewards and research software engineers. Furthermore, the training capacity and training materials on relevant topics should be increased.
- **Infrastructure.** It should be possible for researchers and teachers to make their research and educational materials open and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This requires technical and organisational infrastructure, which must be implemented in collaboration with other universities and (inter)national partners. This infrastructure should facilitate the standardisation of workflows, the creation of metadata and the interoperability of research objects within and across disciplines, allowing geographically dispersed groups of people to collaborate across institutional and academic boundaries.

In designing, implementing and connecting research and education infrastructure, it is crucial to consider its governance and provenance and retain (or retrieve) digital sovereignty through the adherence to guiding principles and supportive legislation and regulations at national and/or European level (e.g. on copyright retention and open licensing).

Policy

Statute of the University

UI

The Regulation for the University of Iceland does not mention Open Science - <https://english.hi.is/node/18642>

VU

Open Science is mentioned in the [VU Strategy Plan 2020-2025](#): “Digitalization is triggering dramatic changes to our educational and research activities, making open science, fair data and open education the new norm.”

Regarding research integrity, VU employees are bound by the [Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#), which contains guidelines for transparent working practices.

UDE

The University of Duisburg-Essen strongly recommends the principle of Open Access in the sense of the Berlin Declaration and supports the further development of the Open Access principle (https://www.uni-due.de/imperia/md/content/zentralverwaltung/verkuendungsblatt_2022/veranz_2022_67.pdf (only in German)).

URV

The statute of the university does not mention Open Science or Open Access. ([Estatut de la URV | Normatives | La Universitat | Universitat Rovira i Virgili](#) - only available in Spanish and Catalan).

Rovira i Virgili University does not reflect support to Open Access principles in its Statute [([Estatut de la URV | Normatives | La Universitat | Universitat Rovira i Virgili](#) - only available in Spanish and Catalan).], but it is included in the II Strategic plan for Research and Innovation (<https://www.urv.cat/media/upload/arxiu/gabinet-comunicacio/plans-estrategics/2nd-strategic-plan-research-innovation-urv.pdf>)

Currently URV is creating the first strategic plan for the office (CRAI) managing Open Science issues.

UIBK

The statute of the university (only available in German) itself does not mention open science or open access. However, it mentions in § 27 that scientific works (theses) have to be put into the repository of the university's library.

Furthermore, the [development plan](#) of the university (only available in German) mentions open science, open access, open educational resources, open data, and open source in a plethora of contexts (5.5.2 digital lifecycle of scientific data; 5.5.3 digital teaching; 5.11.1 Innsbruck University Press; 5.11.3 library; 5.11.6 Information Technology Services; 6.3 faculty for educational sciences; 6.7 faculty of teacher education; 6.10 faculty of political and social sciences).

UNINA

The University of Naples states in its Statute the firm support to the principles of Open access. Article 2, paragraph 11: *The University guarantees the principle of full and open access to scientific literature and promotes the free online dissemination of the results of research produced in the University, to ensure the widest dissemination; participates in the process of building and implementing the "European space of lifelong learning".*

For the Statute of the University of Naples see:

<http://www.unina.it/ateneo/statuto-e-normativa/statuto> (in italian)

UPOL

The statute of the university does not explicitly mention open science and the implementation of its aspects.

Open Science is mentioned and encouraged in the University's Strategic Plan 2021+, specifically in Goal 3: Excellence in Research and Development in article 3.4 Promoting an open science strategy (actualization for 2023), regarding several issues: development of data management plans; dissemination of the knowledge base; promotion of the open science community; building a metadata repository; open access publishing

An important fact to mention with regard to the status of the university is that UPOL is ready to sign The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and join the COARA coalition this year.

UEA

There is no explicit mention of Open Science in the University Statutes.

CBS

Open Science and Open Access are not mentioned in CBS' bylaws nor in its current strategy.

Publications

UI

The University of Iceland [open access policy](#) applies to journal articles.

VU

As of 01-01-2023, a new [Open Access policy](#) went into effect.

UDE

The University of Duisburg-Essen has an Open Access Policy for publications including digitized documents

(https://www.uni-due.de/imperia/md/content/zentralverwaltung/verkuendungsblatt_2022/veranz_2022_67.pdf (only in German)).

URV

The [institutional open access policy](#) states that all university staff (teaching and research staff (PDI) and administration and services staff (PAS)) has to deposit all scientific and academic publications (journal articles, texts presented at conferences, scientific-technical documents, books or book chapters, research reports, etc.) carried out within the framework of their activity at the URV to the institutional repository of the University.

UIBK

The University of Innsbruck expressly supports open access publications and thus the free and sustainable approach to scientific knowledge. Furthermore, UIBK signed the Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities.

To this effect, the University of Innsbruck expects its members (in accordance with the University Act of 2002 §94) to deposit already published publications in the institutional repository of the University of Innsbruck - Open Access, after expiration of the adequate waiting periods. Any new work should be first published directly in open access journals or in the form of open access monographs, if appropriate journals or series with quality assurance procedures (e.g. peer review) can be found. Furthermore, the University of Innsbruck advises its members to also free the access to their research data.

The University of Innsbruck assists its members in the realization of these recommendations through relevant information and advice from the open access contact point at the Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Tirol (*University and State Library of Tyrol*).

Publications that were published through open access will from now on be specifically identified in the research documentation database: <https://www.uibk.ac.at/open-access/policy/index.html.en>

UNINA

For the Guidelines for open access to scientific literature and license for filing in FedOA, with CC 4.0 license (approved by the Senato Accademico on 29.11.2015 and Consiglio di Amministrazione, n. 21, on 30.11.2015) see: <http://www.sba.unina.it/getFile.php?id=468> (in Italian)

UPOL

Amendment n. 10 to the University Statutes regulates the execution of property rights in the context of the licensing of scientific publications. This part of the University Statute outlines the conditions under which authorized employees of the Palacký University (UP) in the Czech Republic can publish their copyrighted works and handle UP's intellectual property rights. In summary, this section of the University Statute specifies the conditions under which authorized employees of UP can publish their works by granting licenses to third parties, subject to certain requirements and limitations. Another significant legal regulation is the internal standard for the handling of copyright works at Palacký University ([R-B-23-03.pdf](#)) issued last year, including in relation to open access publishing. Another internal standard (R-B-18/01) regulates the obligation to establish a scientific identifier (ORCID) for all authors of publications.

UE

The University of East Anglia has had an [institutional policy on Open Access to research publications](#) since 2013. It places requirements on UEA authors for journal articles and conferences proceedings, and encourages open access for all types of research outputs where possible and practicable. The policy has been regularly reviewed and updated. Outputs are made available through the University's EPrints [digital repository](#) and [research portal](#).

CBS

In May 2019, a revised version of CBS' Open Access Policy was published. The policy aims at peer-reviewed journal articles, reviews, and conference papers. The policy favours Green Open Access, but allows for other forms of Open Access publishing. Researchers are required to archive the accepted manuscript of their articles in CBS' institutional repository. The policy and guidelines for Open Access publishing can be accessed here: [CBS Open Access Policy \(2019\)](#) & [OA guidelines](#).

Doctoral dissertations

UI

The University of Iceland has procedural guidance on how to deposit doctoral dissertations, which was approved by the University Council in April 2020. The guidance was made in collaboration with Opin Vísindi, the institutional repository of Icelandic universities and the National and University library of Iceland. The guidance is only available in Icelandic but the purpose of it is to make sure that doctoral dissertations are saved and accessible to the public online without hindrance or charge.

VU

VU dissertations are made publicly available through the [VU Research Portal \(Pure\)](#).

UDE

The publication of doctoral dissertations is based on the doctoral regulations of the faculties of the UDE. There, open access publication is strongly encouraged.

URV

The publication of doctoral dissertations is based on the URV's doctoral regulations "[Academic and registration regulations for doctoral studies](#)", article 32.

Doctoral and other students of URV must deposit their doctoral, master's or bachelor's theses in the institutional repository of the University Once the doctoral thesis has been approved, the

university will take care of its archive in open electronic format in an institutional repository and will send, in electronic format, a copy of this, as well as all the additional information necessary to the Ministry of Universities for the purpose of its publication in a national repository, which will be managed by the General Secretariat of Universities.

UIBK

§ 27 Publication of scientific work

“The publication of scientific papers according to § 86 UG has to be done electronically in the repository of the University and State Library of Tyrol” (translated with DeepL)

<https://www.uibk.ac.at/universitaet/mitteilungsblatt/pdf-dateien/gesamtfassung-satzungsteil-studien-rechtliche-bestimmungen.pdf>

UNINA

Since 2008, calls for admission to doctoral programs require that doctoral theses be made available in open access (article 13: doctoral degree and doctoral thesis, and article 26: thesis filing):

“Doctoral dissertations are published in Open Access in FedOA, at the end of the career or within thirty-six months after discussion, in the cases and according to the procedures provided by the University of Naples' doctoral thesis deposit procedures and in implementation of the CRUI guidelines for the deposit of doctoral theses in open archives”.

For the UNINA regulations governing the doctoral program see:

http://www.unina.it/documents/11958/12030941/2558_29-07-2016.pdf (in Italian)

For the (CRUI) guidelines for the deposit of doctoral theses in open archives see:

https://www.crui.it/images/bibliotche/linee_guida_deposito_tesi_dottorato.pdf (in Italian)

UPOL

Internal standard entitled "Topic assignment, submission and evidence of the bachelor's, master's, dissertation thesis and rigor thesis and the method of their publication" (R-B-17-08-UZ01) regulates in Article 4 the obligation of students to deposit these types of qualification works in the internal student agenda system (STAG) from where these works are further published through the university library catalogue.

UEA

Postgraduate research students are required to deposit an electronic copy of their thesis in the University's EPrints digital repository; this process is mediated by Library staff. By default theses are made openly accessible but may be embargoed if necessary.

CBS

The “Programme regulations for the PhD School at Copenhagen Business School” from 2020 state that Open Access to doctoral dissertations is mandatory.

Research data

UI

“UI's Strategy for the period 2021-2026 (UI26) states that the University will develop a clear vision that encourages interdisciplinary work and increased research impact” and states that the default rule of data is that it should be as open as possible. The University also has responsibility to preserve data that complies with FAIR Principles. This strategy is ongoing and has not been implemented at this point. “The Icelandic Social Science Data Service, DATICE, founded in 2018, provides UI staff with services and assistance in preparing data for open access. DATICE will, along with other open repositories at UI, play a key role in strengthening open science services at the University.” [Open Access Policy | University of Iceland \(hi.is\)](#)

VU

VU has a university-wide [Research Data Management policy](#). Furthermore, several faculties have created more [specific policies](#) for their respective faculty employees.

UDE

The University of Duisburg-Essen has a research data management (RDM) policy: Leitlinien zum Umgang mit Forschungsdaten an der Universität Duisburg-Essen (https://www.uni-due.de/imperia/md/content/zentralverwaltung/verkuendungsblatt_2019/vbl_2019_18.pdf only in German)).

URV

Universitat Rovira i Virgili has an Institutional policy on open access to research data [[Pol.ins.acces obert recercaang.pdf \(urv.cat\)](#)]: "RESEARCH DATA= information, in particular facts or numbers, collected for examination and analysis for subsequent interpretation, discussion and calculation. It also refers to underlying data and other data such as unpublished "cooked" data, but not to raw data. It includes data, metadata and the tools for consulting them. As examples, it includes statistics, experimental results, measures, fieldwork observations, survey results, recorded interviews and images. The present policy focuses on research data in digital format."

UIBK

A basic regulation on intellectual property rights (IPR) is included in the employment contract between researchers and the university. IPR can also use further. If the University of Innsbruck is the owner of the intellectual property rights, it has the right to decide on the possible publication and disclosure of the research data together with the researchers. In accordance with the specifications of this policy, relevant research data must be stored and made available in suitable global or national subject-specific repositories or in the institutional repository of the University of Innsbruck. The research data must be provided with persistent identifiers. The minimum storage period for research data and recordings is 10 years after the assignment of a persistent identifier or after the publication of the relevant work or after completion of the research activities. The responsibility for research data management during and after the research activities lies with the University of Innsbruck and the individual researchers.

Research Data Management Policy:

<https://www.uibk.ac.at/universitaet/mitteilungsblatt/2021-2022/32.html#h2-4>

Storage Policies for the institutional research data repository: <https://doi.org/10.48323/jxxcd-6pa23>

Terms of use for the institutional research data repository: <https://doi.org/10.48323/c8hdv-hx728>

UNINA

For the *Research data* see the Guidelines for open access to scientific literature and license for filing in FedOA, with CC 4.0 license (approved by the Senato Accademico on 29.11.2015 and Consiglio di Amministrazione, n. 21, on 30.11.2015): <http://www.sba.unina.it/getFile.php?id=468>

UPOL

Research data management policy is the main deliverable of the Research policy and support department and its associate work group in 2023. There is already one published within [CATRIN](#) (The Czech Advanced Technology and Research Institute - part of UPOL, uploaded to Teamworks) but the general one will be delivered before the end of 2023.

A large research of top performing institutions and their research policies has been carried out, sub-elements suitable for implementation have been identified and the working group is currently working on evaluating and building the basic structure of the new policy. This policy will directly reflect the F.A.I.R. principles of research data management.

UEA

The University of East Anglia has had a Research Data Management policy in place since 2013. This policy is regularly reviewed and updated; the latest version of the policy can be accessed from the Research and Innovation section on this page:

<https://www.uea.ac.uk/about/university-information/university-policies>. The policy is complemented by a guidance document which provides more detail on how to comply with the policy.

CBS

CBS has had a Research Data Management policy since 2017. The policy can be accessed here: [CBS RDM Policy \(2017\)](#). The current policy is revised during the academic year 2023/24.

Educational resources

UI

The University of Iceland has a platform called UicelandX which is for developing and delivering MOOCs to a global audience, this is in collaboration with edX.org and the courses are open and free. [edX | University of Iceland \(hi.is\)](#)

VU

VU does not yet have a policy for Open Educational Resources.

UDE

The University of Duisburg-Essen has a policy on the development and use of Open Educational Resources (OER):

(https://www.uni-due.de/imperia/md/content/zentralverwaltung/verkuendungsblatt_2022/veranz_2022_65.pdf) (only in German).

URV

Institutional open access policy

(https://www.urv.cat/media/upload/arxiu/crai/politica_acces_obert.pdf): it states that all university staff (teaching and research staff (PDI) and administration and services staff (PAS)) has to deposit all scientific and academic publications (journal articles, texts presented at conferences, scientific-technical documents, books or book chapters, research reports, etc.) carried out within the framework of their activity at the URV to the institutional repository of the University.

UIBK

"The University of Innsbruck will support national and international efforts to promote Open Educational Resources (OER). It cooperates with other Austrian universities in setting up an OER repository for storing OER and actively supports the establishment of a national certification body for OER. In addition to the primary goal of providing high-quality materials, the OER Repository also supports the transparent and positive presentation of high-quality teaching concepts" (University of Innsbruck (2022 – 2027), Development Plan, pp. 36). UIBK recommends that all university members use, create and publish OER, under the premise that the free educational materials are relevant to academic teaching and meet scientific standards. UIBK supports its members in the use, creation and publication of OER in the form of advisory services, training courses and the provision of information material.

Policy for Open Educational Resources:

<https://www.uibk.ac.at/universitaet/mitteilungsblatt/2021-2022/32.html#h2-3> (Only in German).

UNINA

For the *Open access educational resources* see the regulations of the University Center "Federica Weblearning" (<https://www.federica.eu/>).

For the decree establishing the University Center "Federica Weblearning" (2015) see: http://www.unina.it/documents/11958/7856170/2866_1108.pdf (in Italian)

For Regulations for the organization and operation of the University Service Center "Federica Weblearning" (2022) see:

https://www.unina.it/documents/11958/28244542/DR_2669_2022_FWL.pdf (in Italian)

For "Federica Weblearning" Terms and Conditions (last update 2022) see:

<https://www.federica.eu/termini-e-condizioni/> (in Italian)

UPOL

UPOL uses Moodle and Edis (own software) for learning objects, each faculty has its own process / system.

UEA

The University does not currently have a policy on Open Educational Resources, but such resources can be added to Pure and made available through the University's EPrints digital repository (<https://ueaeprints.uea.ac.uk/>) and research portal (<https://research-portal.uea.ac.uk/en/>).

CBS

CBS does not yet have a policy for Open Educational Resources.

Digitized documents

UI

Electronic catalogue of manuscripts preserved in the National and University Library of Iceland, the Árni Magnússon Institute in Reykjavík and the Arnamagnæan Institute in Copenhagen (Den Arnamagnæanske Samling) on [Home | Handrit.is](#).

[Timarit.is](#) is a collaborative project between the National Library of the Faroe Islands, National and Public Library of Greenland and National and University Library of Iceland.

[Rafhlaðan](#) is an electronic depository for longtime preservation of the National and University Library of Iceland.

VU

The VU Open Access policy covers digitized documents.

UDE

The University of Duisburg-Essen has an Open Access Policy for publications including digitized documents

(https://www.uni-due.de/imperia/md/content/zentralverwaltung/verkuendungsblatt_2022/veranz_2022_67.pdf (only in German)).

URV

The repository of the URV serves Rovira i Virgili University as the digital repository for the institution's research output created by the members of the URV. This includes unpublished articles (preprints), peer-reviewed articles (postprints), published articles, research datasets, end-of-degree and end-of-masters theses, doctoral theses, teaching materials, and other documents that may be of interest. [[Institutional Repository URV](#)]

UIBK

n/a

UNINA

For the *Digitized documents* see the Guidelines for open access to scientific literature and license for filing in FedOA, with CC 4.0 license (approved by the Senato Accademico on 29.11.2015 and Consiglio di Amministrazione, n. 21, on 30.11.2015): <http://www.sba.unina.it/getFile.php?id=468> (in Italian)

UPOL

The University does not have internal rules for the storage and long-term preservation of digital documents in the sense of scientific publications. There is a valid Filing and Shredding Code which regulates this issue in a general sense, but it concerns rather digitized documents of administrative character.

Methodologically, the obligation to store the full texts of publication results in the internal system of publication activity records (OBD) is regulated in case such a result is published on an open access platform allowing this green OA method.

UEA

The University's Information Classification and Data Management Policy covers the issue of digitised assets in a general sense; this would apply to research as well as administrative documents:

<https://www.uea.ac.uk/documents/20142/577003/Information+classification+policy+v5.0.pdf>

CBS

CBS does not have a policy for digitised research documents. All born-digital or digitised administrative documents are stored and documented on an internal documentation server.

Long-term preservation of research outputs

UI

[Rafhlaðan](#) is an electronic depository for longtime preservation of the National and University Library of Iceland.

[DATICE](#) is a data service and archive for Icelandic social science research data. Our goal is to ensure open and free access to scientific data for the research community and the general public. The service is located at the Social Science Research Institute (SSRI) within the University of Iceland.

The National Archives implement public policy on archiving and records management and serve a public archive.

VU

The [VU RDM policy](#) states that: "Researchers are responsible for archiving their research data for a minimum of ten years after research results are published, unless legal requirements, discipline-specific guidelines or contractual arrangements dictate otherwise."

UDE

The long-term availability of publications, dissertations and related research data published via DuEPublico (institutional repository for scientific publications) is provided by the German National Library.

URV

The repository of the URV serves Rovira i Virgili University as the digital repository for the institution's research output created by the members of the URV. This includes unpublished articles (preprints), peer-reviewed articles (postprints), published articles, research datasets, end-of-degree and end-of-masters theses, doctoral theses, teaching materials, and other documents that may be of interest. The URV institutional repository guarantees perpetual access and preservation of its files by storing them in secure servers of the university and it meets the technical requirements to ensure interoperability with other information systems. [[Institutional repository](#) | [Learning and Research Resource Centre \(CRAI\)](#) | [Universitat Rovira i Virgili](#) | [Home \(urv.cat\)](#)]

UIBK

For e-journals and e-book series published by the university via institutional repository.
For research data, open educational resources, and digitized historical documentation the long-term strategy is based on <https://www.archivematica.org/>

UNINA

For the Long-term preservation of publications and data the University of Naples on 26/11/2012 entered into a formal Agreement with "Magazzini Digital", the national conservation and long-term access service for digital resources. See <https://www.depositolegale.it/editori-aderenti/>

UPOL

See previous UPOL input in the Digitized documents section. Ensuring the long-term availability of publication outputs in open repositories is usually insured by the conditions of the grant and project providers themselves.

UEA

Not covered by policy but part of the T&Cs relating to the institution repository.

CBS

CBS RDM policy addresses the long-term preservation of research data: "In accordance with the *Danish Code of Conduct for Research Integrity*, researchers must ensure that research data selected for long-term preservation remain archived for a minimum of five years after project completion. Researchers working with personal data must archive their research data at the Danish National Archives (Rigsarkivet), unless Danish legislation states that the research data must be destroyed upon project completion." (CBS RDM Policy, 2017)

Documents published on the Internet are harvested by [Netarkivet](#) that collects and preserves the Danish part of the Internet and preserves it in their web archive in relation to the Danish Legal Deposit Act.

Participation in national and international networks on Open Science

UI

AURORA Universities Network (<https://aurora-network.global/>) and previously the Aurora Calileo Network.

VU

VU is active in several networks:

- A national Open Science roundtable with stakeholders (<https://www.openscience.nl/en/home-2/>).
- [Open Science NL](#), a recently launched national initiative that governs investments in national ambitions on Open Science with government funding.
- AURORA Universities Network (<https://aurora-network.global/>).

UDE

The University of Duisburg-Essen participates in the international AURORA Universities Network (<https://aurora-network.global/>). The University of Duisburg-Essen is member of the national NFDI e. V. (<https://www.nfdi.de/>) and contributes to several NFDI consortia (NFDI4CS, KonsortSWD, NFDI4Immuno, FAIRmat, NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Health, NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Microbiota, Text+). The University of Duisburg-Essen is a member of the state network digitale Hochschule NRW (<https://www.dh.nrw/>). In this context the university participates in state initiatives like openaccess.nrw (<https://openaccess.nrw/>), fdm.nrw (<https://www.fdm.nrw/>) and orca.nrw (<https://www.orca.nrw/>).

URV

- Catalan network: Open Science Working Group of CSUC (Consortium of University Services of Catalonia) [<https://www.csuc.cat/ca/serveis/ciencia-oberta>]
- Spanish network: CRUE (Conference of Rectors of Spanish Universities) Working Group on Repositories [<https://www.rebiun.org/grupos-trabajo/repositorios>]

UIBK

- **AUSSDA - The Austrian Social Science Data Archive** <https://aussda.at/en/>; other participating universities are: Universität Wien, Karl-Franzen-Universität Graz, Johannes Kepler Universität Linz
- **AT2OA² Austrian Transition to Open Access 2:**

https://www.at2oa.at/at2oa2_home.html Other participating universities: Akademie der bildenden Künste Wien, Donau Universität Krems, Research Institute of Molecular Pathology, IST Austria, Kunst Uni Graz, Kunst Universität Linz, Med Uni Graz, Medizinische Universität Innsbruck, Medizinische Universität Wien, Montan Universität, Uni Mozarteum, TU Graz, TU Wien, Die Angewandte, BOKU, Universität für Musik und Darstellende Kunst Wien, Uni Graz, Alpen-Adria Universität Klagenfurt, Johannes-Kepler-Universität Linz, Universität Salzburg, Universität Wien, Vetmed Uni Vienna, Wirtschaftsuniversität Wien

- **FAIR Data Austria:**

<https://forschungsdaten.at/fda/>; together with Technische Universität Graz, Technische Universität Wien, Universität Wien, Universität Innsbruck, Medizinische Universität Graz, Akademie der Bildenden Künste Wien, and 23 associated partners.

- **AURORA European Universities Alliance:**

<https://aurora-universities.eu/>; other participating universities are: Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Universitat Rovira i Virgili, University of Napoli Federico II, University of East Anglia, Palacký University Olomouc, The University of Iceland, Universität Duisburg-Essen, Copenhagen Business School, Université Paris-Est Créteil Val de Marne

UNINA

- **CRUI (Conference of University Rectors)**

Open Access Group (2006-2020) -> Observatory on Open Science (2020 to present):

(<https://osa.crui.it/>)

- **Universities SHARE**

(www.sharecampus.it); Scholarly Heritage and Access to Research is the access network of shared library services of the universities: Naples Federico II, Naples "L'Orientale", Naples "Parthenope", Naples Suor Orsola Benincasa, Salerno, Sannio and Basilicata, University Campania Luigi Vanvitelli.

- **AURORA Universities Network**

(<https://aurora-network.global/>); other participating universities are: Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, The Universitat Rovira i Virgili, University of Innsbruck, University of East Anglia, Palacký University Olomouc, The University of Iceland, Universität Duisburg-Essen, University of Aberdeen, Copenhagen Business School, Université Grenoble Alpes.

- **Galileo for Open Science**

Network of Stewards and Navigation Interface for the World of Open Science "OS Galileo"; other participating universities: The University of Iceland, Pavol Jozef Šafárik University, Palacký University, University of Tetova

UPOL

- **AURORA Universities Network**

- **CZARMA** - Czech derivative of the EARMA (European Association of Research Managers and Administrators), especially its Open Science workgroup

- **Open Science Workgroup within the Association of University Libraries of the Czech Republic**

- **EOSC-CZ** (<https://www.e-infra.cz/eosc>) and its working groups for the implementation of EOSC in the Czech republic

- **INOSC** (<https://osc-international.com>) - International Network of Open Science & Scholarship Communities

- **P JAC** (Programme Johannes Amos Comenius) project **Open Science I** - prepared huge national project for building National Repository Platform for research data (<https://opjak.cz/en/documents>)

- **Czech eLib** (<https://www.czechelib.cz/cs/>) - UPOL as member of this The CzechELib National Centre which ensures the purchase of key electronic resources for the entire research and education community in the Czech Republic, takes care of their management, including usage statistics, and supports open access publishing.

UEA

- UEA is part of the UK Reproducibility Network (UKRN)

- The UEA Library is a member of the UK Research Libraries group (UKRL)

CBS

- [Danish Network for Open Access](#)
- [Danish Research Data Management Network](#)
- [National coordination and implementation of the national FAIR strategy](#) (since September 2021)
- [Skills for the European Open Science commons: creating a training ecosystem for Open and FAIR science \(Skills4EOSC\)](#), September 2022-September 2025
- [AURORA European Universities Alliance](#)

Cost monitoring

UI

Costs are recorded and monitored to an extent.

The University is part of the Iceland Consortium for national access to academic and scholarly content, costs are monitored by the IC. The Uoi monitors costs for institutional subscriptions, ie. subscriptions outside the IC.

VU

The University Library monitors the costs for Open Access and (to some extent) FAIR Data and Software.

UDE

The costs covered by the University Library are recorded by the University Library.

URV

URV follow precise procedures for monitoring the costs of:

- Publication of articles and journals with commercial publishers
- Article Processing Charges (APC) required by commercial publishers for having articles available in open access
- Subscriptions of electronic resources

The costs of publishing in open access can be found through the university's accounting system

UIBK

OA publishing in established publishers' journals: Agreements with publishers.

“The University and Regional Library of Tyrol in cooperation with the Kooperation E-Medien Österreich (Austrian Academic Library Consortium) is aiming to negotiate contracts with publishers that enable university members to publish their research results in renowned open access journals either free of charge or with reduced APCs.

Open Access Gold is the primary publication of a scientific text via an online medium, often a renowned journal. This way, the scientific text becomes openly accessible worldwide.

[...] The open access publications financed by the agreements are continuously made available in the university's repository for publications. An overview of the publications can be found here:

<https://diglib.uibk.ac.at/ulbtirola/nav/classification/4500227>”

<https://www.uibk.ac.at/open-access/finanzieren/publizieren-in-oa-zeitschriften/>

UNINA

Costs of electronic resources are recorded by the University Center for Libraries; Publication costs for articles and books are recorded at departments levels; APCs costs are monitored by the Conference of Italian Rectors with regard to “transformative contracts” negotiated at national level, by Federico II departments with regard to contracts with publishers not negotiated at national level.

UPOL

Costs like APCs are monitored within the Czech eLib Platform, at UPOL administered by each faculty on specific analytical accounts.

UEA

The UEA has signed up to a number of transitional Read and Publish agreements. These are negotiated on a national level in the UK by Jisc, and one of the requirements of the deals is to ensure overall costs relating to accessing subscription journal content and open access publishing are constrained. APCs paid from funders' open access block grants are also monitored.

CBS

The costs are monitored internally at CBS Library. The information is not openly available.

Recognition and rewards

UI

Not available at the present.

VU

VU is part of a [national programme on changing the system of recognizing and rewarding academics](#). The VU has a [Recognition & Rewards implementation team](#) that works on revising promotion/ career track policies, in collaboration with the faculties. In June 2023, VU adopted a revised framework for [Academic Career Paths](#).

UDE

Currently not available.

URV

[Transformative agreements and other aid - Open access - CRAI guides and tutorials at Universitat Rovira i Virgili \(urv-libguides-com.translate.goog\)](#)

URV in order to encourage open access and help researchers deal with these APCs, the URV and other entities have launched a series of grants that you can consult below.

- Transformative agreements: transformative agreements signed with the publishers ACS , Elsevier , Springer Nature , Wiley , AIP and Emerald URV authors can publish for free in open access in some of their journals.
- OPEN URV call [[Ajuts OPEN per publicar articles científics en accés obert | Universitat Rovira i Virgili \(urv.cat\)](#)]
- Other discounts
- *Open Research Europe*

UIBK

“Not all open access journals charge publication fees for the publication of articles; especially non-commercial publishers often receive institutional funding. However, many publishers and journals are relying on article processing charges (APC) as a business model for open access. To assist the University of Innsbruck's scientists financially and organizationally, a central publishing fund for the co-financing of those charges of open access journals was created.

The funds of the publishing fund of the University of Innsbruck are allocated by the vice rectorate for research in consideration of the allocation guidelines and criteria for funding.

UNINA

For the moment, there are no rewards for researchers who publish in Open Access.

UPOL

At UPOL there is no centralized APC fund, financial resources for the long-term concept for the development of universities are (according to internal rules) distributed to the faculties to be used accordingly.

UPOL has an annual competition for the Rector's Prize for authors of scientific monographs, which, however, does not take into account the open approach of publishing

UEA

The University is currently looking into the role of Open Research in reward and recognition and is involved in a UKRN project looking into this, along with a number of other UK Higher Education institutions. The UEA is a signatory to DORA.

CBS

CBS has clear and transparent guidelines for research assessment. Open Science does not play a role in this.

Community Engagement

UI

Currently not available.

VU

VU has a dedicated RDM and Open Science community manager, who visits RDM expertise meetings and conferences at home and abroad and takes care of the proper dissemination of the latest knowledge throughout VU Amsterdam.

VU has a vibrant RDM support community of library experts, (faculty) data stewards, legal professionals, IT support, grant advisors and knowledge transfer officers. This group meets regularly to discuss issues regarding Research Data Support.

In addition, the VU Open Science programme supports several academic communities:

- [Open Science Community Amsterdam](#)
- [ReproducibiliTea VU Amsterdam](#)
- [Student Initiative for Open Science](#)
- [Pizza4Python](#)
- [Medical Data plus Pizza Meetups](#)

All of these grassroots initiatives have links with VU, however, they are independent of the RDM community.

UDE

The University Library Duisburg-Essen has a project group FAIR Science (<https://www.uni-due.de/ub/fair/>). An Open Science Community is in preparation.

URV

Currently not available.

UIBK

Currently not available.

UNINA

The University Centre for Libraries has been working together with numerous communities of researchers, inside and outside the University Federico II, for about 15 years to:

- support them in the practice of open access publication of research results;
- guide them in the use of platforms for journal and series publication;
- advise them on how to publish research data;

- advise them on the publication strategies to adopt.

From them the Center receives continuous input on new goals to be realised (<http://www.sba.unina.it/index.php?it/142/open-access-open-science>).

UPOL

According to INOSC guidance programme an open science community has been established at the university, which is being developed this year into partial plans of activities including its own communication platform, involvement of leaders and experts, popularization and communication of science and other elements through which Palacký University wants to profile itself as a leader in this field.

UEA

Open research forms part of the remit of the University's Research Culture group, which meets regularly to discuss issues on an institutional level. There are also ReproducibiliTea events organised by the institutional UKRN representatives.

CBS

At CBS, academic officers from different administrative units that support researchers like the Research Support Office, Legal, IT, Library) collaborate closely with one another across the organisation.

In spring 2023, CBS participated in the INOSC incubator program. This has led to the establishment of the OSC Copenhagen with a local branch at CBS.

Support & Training

UI

The National and University of Iceland library offer training to PhD students on a regular basis, training and presentations available to Schools and departments upon request.

Information and material available on intraweb.

The library also has a manual about open science, but it's only available in icelandic: [Opinn aðgangur - Rannsóknarþjónusta og opinn aðgangur - Leiðarvísar.is at Landsbókasafn Íslands – Háskólabókasafn \(leidarvísar.is\)](#)

VU

VU offers several trainings and workshops on Open Science practices (available via the [PhD portal](#) and the [Library event page](#)). These include:

- *DMPonline* - how to write a data management plan
- *YoDa* - how to use the YourData (YoDa) storage/ archiving infrastructure
- *OSF* - how to use the Open Science Framework research management infrastructure
- *Carpentries workshops* - how to get started with shell, git, Python and R.
- *CodeRefinery workshops* - how to increase your skill in collaborative programming

UDE

The University Library Duisburg-Essen organizes the course series Publication Days once a year (<https://www.uni-due.de/gcplus/de/publicationdays.php>) and offers the online course DataCampus – Discover the data (https://www.uni-due.de/ub/datacampus/discover_the_data.php). The Research Data Services at UDE offer Research Data Management (RDM) support and a RDM curriculum with regular trainings and online self-learning material for RDM

(<https://www.uni-due.de/rds/fdm-curriculum.php> and <https://moodle.uni-due.de/course/view.php?id=20309>). These include:

- Basic research data management course for PhD students and other interested persons with three different focus topics: “electronic lab notebooks & sensitive data”, “sensitive data,

text, audio & video data”, or “electronic lab notebooks, scripts & code”. The course covers the topics data management plans, metadata, data organization, storage, and publication.

- Data reuse & reusable data - about finding data, reusing data, and making own data reusable.
- eLabFTW Hands-on - introduction to the electronic lab notebook eLabFTW.
- Coscine Hands-on - introduction to the research data management platform Coscine for FAIR data.
- OSF - introduction to the Open Science Framework (OSF).
- Project management with GitLab - how to use GitLab for project management.
- RDM with Git & GitLab - how to use the version control software Git and the web based platform GitLab to do good research data management.
- Reproducible analysis workflows - introduction to reusable data analysis using Snakemake workflows.
- Reuse of copyright protected research data - how to handle copyright protected data.
- R Notebooks - introduction to reproducible analyses in the statistical software R using R Notebooks.

URV

[File - SwafS WP6 Sharing and implementing Open Science practices - Aurora Alliance \(teamwork.com\)](#)

UIBK

In-service training and lectures are organized regularly.

Open Access: Open Access Publishing – Services, Financing, Consultations:

<https://www.uibk.ac.at/open-access/>

Research Data: in planning

OER: MOOC on use and production of OER <https://imoox.at/course/oermoooc>

Other than that, researchers and staff have access to training of the FAIR-project.

The university wants to establish training in the field of Git, Open Journal System, Omeka-S, and data modelling.

UNINA

1. **Courses on Open Science** organized by the **Libraries Center “Roberto Pettorino”** for students, doctoral students, postdocs, researchers. Annual frequency.
2. **MOOC** on Research Data Management, Open Badge e Open Science published by **EMMA - European Multiple Mooc Aggregator**.

UPOL

As far as open science education is concerned, the university organizes regular courses through the university library focusing on the basics of open science, namely open access and F.A.I.R. data. The courses are primarily aimed at students and junior researchers.

At the same time, the library operates a university open science portal (<https://openscience.upol.cz/>) serving as a gateway for basic orientation in this area.

The third element of education through the library is the provision of individual counseling.

The Research Support and Policy Office within the Rector's Office as one of its agendas is developing the Open Science Community Olomouc (OSCO) and promoting Open Science with the plans of further lecturing, courses and workshops on the OS theme.

The OSCO itself should serve as a platform for decentralized open science education through mutual sharing of experiences and good practices.

Another element contributing to providing the necessary support in this area is to build a knowledge hub (on the university wiki) as a curated list of internal and external resources such as learning kits, tutorials, tools and applications, guides and recommended practices. This should be heavily synergized with Aurora RI 6.2 deliverable.

UEA

Open Research training is provided for postgraduate students via the Personal and Professional Development programme. These are offered on a faculty level to allow for differences in disciplinary needs, though they are open to doctoral students across faculties. Training is provided for staff on request; this is often organised within a School. Training is offered on Research Data Management and Open Access; both incorporate other aspects of Open Research.

CBS

CBS offers several trainings and workshops on Open Science practices, mostly focusing on research data management and scholarly communication. These include:

- General introduction to RDM for social scientists (all researchers, every semester, offered by the RDM Support)
- Data management planning (all researchers, every semester, offered by the RDM Support)
- FAIR data (all researchers, every semester, offered by the RDM Support)
- Introduction to RDM for PhD students (PhD students, every semester, offered by the RDM Support)
- Advanced RDM for PhD students (PhD students, once a year, offered by the RDM Support as part of the “Craft of Research” course)
- [eLearning course about Research Data Management](#) (all researchers, online self-study)
- [How to FAIR](#) (all researchers, online self-study)

Infrastructure

Repositories

UI

University Press: www.haskolautgafan.is - does not have an open access policy.

Institutional repositories for research information (CRIS): <https://iris.rais.is>

Institutional repositories for publications: www.opinvisindi.is

Institutional repositories for doctoral dissertations: www.opinvisindi.is

Platforms for the publication of open access scientific journals: www.ojs.hi.is

Platforms for the publication of open access e-book series: Not available.

Platforms for open educational resources: <https://english.hi.is/edx>

Platforms for popularisation of scientific research: www.visindavefur.is (www.why.is),

<https://english.hi.is/frettir>

Platforms for digitised historical documentation: www.handrit.is, www.timarit.is and

www.rafladan.is

VU

University Press

Current Research Information System: [Pure](#) Research Portal

Institutional repositories for publications: [Pure](#) Research Portal

Institutional repositories for doctoral dissertations: [Pure](#) Research Portal

Platforms for the publication of open access scientific journals: [openjournals](#)

Platforms for the publication of open access e-book series: Not available.

Platforms for open educational resources: <https://edusources.nl/>

Platforms for popularisation of scientific research: <https://openresearch.amsterdam/>

Platforms for digitised historical documentation: <https://vu.contentdm.oclc.org/>

UDE

University Press: Unavailable

Institutional repositories for research information (CRIS): in preparation

Institutional repositories for publications: DuEPublico <https://duepublico2.uni-due.de>

Institutional repositories for research data: Currently DuEPublico <https://duepublico2.uni-due.de> is also used for research data. Dataverse instance is in preparation. For archiving of research data without publication or metadata publications with data available on request the repository RADAR by FIZ Karlsruhe (<https://www.radar-service.eu/radar/de/search>) is used.

Institutional repositories for doctoral dissertations: DuEPublico <https://duepublico2.uni-due.de>

Platforms for the publication of open access scientific journals: <https://ojs.ub.uni-due.de/>; OJS is used exclusively for the editorial process. Available since ca. 2017. The publication of the documents takes place on DuEPublico (<https://duepublico2.uni-due.de>).

Platforms for the publication of open access e-book series: Forthcoming

Platforms for open educational resources: DuEPublico <https://duepublico2.uni-due.de/content/oer>

Platforms for popularization of scientific research: Unavailable

Platforms for digitized historical documentation: Unavailable

URV

University Press: <https://www.urv.cat/ca/recerca/produccio-cientifica/publicacions-urv/publicar/>.

Institutional repositories for research information (CRIS): [iPublic | scimarina \(urv.cat\)](https://www.urv.cat/en/urv/research-information)

Institutional repositories for publications: <https://repositori.urv.cat/fourrepopublic/>

Institutional repositories for doctoral dissertations: <https://repositori.urv.cat/fourrepopublic/>;
<https://www.tdx.cat/handle/10803/311>

Platforms for the publication of open access scientific journals: Unavailable

Platforms for the publication of open access e-book series: Unavailable

Platforms for open educational resources: Unavailable

Platforms for popularization of scientific research: <https://www.comciencia.urv.cat/>

Platforms for digitized historical documentation: <https://mdc.csuc.cat/>

UIBK

Innsbruck University Press

<https://www.uibk.ac.at/open-access/publizieren/iup/>

<https://www.uibk.ac.at/iup/open-access> (available only in German) Specific policy to support open access publication since 01.03.2017

148 open access publications until now, among them:

<https://www.uibk.ac.at/iup/open-access.html.de>

15 journals <https://www.uibk.ac.at/iup/verlagsverzeichnis/zeitschriften.html>

Digitale Bibliothek:

<https://diglib.uibk.ac.at/ulbtirola/>; Visual Library (Software), ca. 2100 documents and ca. 4100 master theses and doctoral dissertations

Service Point for Research Data Management

<https://researchdata.uibk.ac.at/>, Invenio RDM, started in March 2022

Local Repository for Digital Humanities based on "WissKi" (<https://wiss-ki.eu/>)

OAPEN – Online library and publication platform:

<https://www.oapen.org/>

OER Repository:

<https://oer-repo.uibk.ac.at>

still under development thus not always online.

Cooperation with iMooX:

(platform for OER MOOCs)

<https://imoox.at/partner/uniinnsbruck/>; Courses: Zeit:shift, Aqua MOOC, Vielfalter:

Tagfalter-Monitoring, MeKoMOOC20: Medienkompetenz in der Lehre, Limnologie: Ökologie des Wassers

Project: Open Education Austria Advanced (OEAA):

<https://www.openeducation.at>; OER-Metadata-Aggregation

Wissenschaftsvermittlung: (Science Outreach)

<https://www.uibk.ac.at/de/public-relations/wissenschaftsvermittlung/> (available only in German);

The communications office gathers the different outreach activities of the university on this website.

Newsroom: <https://www.uibk.ac.at/newsroom/>; The latest news regarding research as well as other news concerning the university is published in the newsroom.

UNINA

University Press:

1. **ClioPress** (<http://www.cliopress.unina.it/>) since 2003, then merged into FedOA Press since 2012.

2. **FedOA - Federico II Open Access University Press**
(<http://www.fedoabooks.unina.it/index.php/fedoapress>)

FedOAPress Federico II Open Access University Press, year of activation 2003; 220 open access publications (updated 02.02.22), since 2015 it hosts the publications of the universities participating in the SHARE project (Universities of Naples Federico II, Naples L'Orientale, Naples Parthenope, Naples Suor Orsola Benincasa, Campania Vanvitelli, Salerno, Sannio and Basilicata). From 2020 it hosts the publications of the Society of Naturalists in Naples and from 2021 the CEA. University Publishing Center of the University of Cassino and Southern Lazio.

Institutional repositories for research information (CRIS):

- **IRIS FedOA**
(<https://www.iris.unina.it/>)

Institutional repositories for publications:

1. **FedOA - Federico II Open Archive** (<http://www.fedoa.unina.it/>)
2. **IRIS FedOA** (<https://www.iris.unina.it/>)
3. **Reti Medievali Open Archive** (<http://www.rmoa.unina.it/>)
4. **e-LIS- e-prints in Library & information Science** (<http://eprints.rclis.org/>)

Institutional repositories for doctoral dissertations:

- **FedOA - Federico II Open Archive** (<http://www.fedoa.unina.it/>)

Institutional repositories for research data and / or for Linked Open Data:

- **Share Catalog** (<https://catalogo.share-cat.unina.it/sharecat/clusters>);
- **Share-VDE (Virtual Discovery Environment)**
(https://wiki.share-vde.org/wiki/Main_Page);

A repository for research data is under construction.

Platforms for the publication of open access scientific journals:

- **SeReNa (System for electronic peer-Reviewed journals @ university of Naples)/ Share Journals** (<http://www.serena.unina.it/>)

Platforms for the publication of open access e-book series:

- **FedOA Books/ Share Books** (<http://www.fedoabooks.unina.it/index.php/fedoapress>)

Platforms for open educational resources:

1. **Federica Web Learning** (<https://www.federica.eu/>)
2. **EMMA - European Multiple Mooc Aggregator** (<https://platform.europeanmoocs.eu/>)

Platforms for popularisation of scientific research:

- **Ciak si Scienza** <https://www.ciaksiscienza.com/ambiente-sostenibilita/>)

Platforms for digitised historical documentation:

- **eCo (Digital collections of the University of Naples Federico II)**
(<http://www.eco.unina.it/>)
- **Botanical Garden Digital Library**
(<http://www.ortobotanico.unina.it/OBN4/mv/biblioteca/biblioteca.htm>)
- **Centro Musa-Reggia di Portici** (<https://www.centromusa.it/it/mediateche.html>)

- **Illuminated Dante Project** (<https://www.dante.unina.it/public/frontend>)
- **DETAIL (Digital Editions Tools And Integrated Lod framework)** (<http://www.detail.unina.it/index.html>)
- **Monasterium.net** (<https://www.icar-us.eu/en/cooperation/online-portals/monasterium-net/>)
- **CO:OP – UNINA. The Creative Archives’ and Users’ Network** (<http://www.coop-unina.org/>)

UPOL

Palacký University Press (<https://www.vydavatelstvi.upol.cz/en/>)

There are more than twenty journals published within Palacký University Press (<https://www.vydavatelstvi.upol.cz/o-nas/periodika-up/>), the most of them are undergoing heavy transformation into the pure Open Access regime.

There is no particular CRIS at the UPOL at the moment, research agendas are administered by specific information systems, such as the Personal Bibliographic Database (OBD) for the registration of publication results, EasyGrants for the registration of project activities, STAG for student affairs, SAP for financial matters, ARL for the operation of the library system, and others. Results of applied research that lead to commercialization are registered by the Science and Technology Park, which deals with technology transfer.

The OBD serves as primary IS for the recording of publications metadata and the Open Access full texts as well. At UPOL we are developing the DSpace publication repository which should serve as a broker to the international platforms and for the grants and projects goals as well.

Scholarly works are recorded within the student agenda STAG and subsequently published through the university library catalogue (<https://library.upol.cz/arl-upol/en/search/>)

Palacký University Press uses the proprietary Actavia platform (<https://www.actavia.cz/>), which handles the entire publishing process, including the peer review process.

Palacký University Press uses for this purpose its one [eshop](#) where open access e-books are offered for download and distribution.

UPOL uses standard communication channels like social media (Twitter, Youtube, Facebook) to communicate its activities. We are currently discussing a new ways of communicating science in conjunction with the open science community through audio-visuals such as short performances, interviews and podcasts.

Platforms for digitized historical documentation: There is no such platform on the central level, but the particular fields like art history, archaeology and theology use specialized resources for these purposes.

UEA

University Press: Boiler House Press (print only)

Institutional repositories for research information (CRIS): <https://research-portal.uea.ac.uk/en/>

Institutional repositories for publications: UEA Eprints ueaeprints.uea.ac.uk

Institutional repositories for research data: UEA Pure <https://research-portal.uea.ac.uk/en/datasets/>

Institutional repositories for doctoral dissertations: UEA Eprints ueaeprints.uea.ac.uk

Platforms for the publication of open access scientific journals: newareastudies.com, a journal led by UEA researchers

Platforms for the publication of open access e-book series: n/a

Platforms for open educational resources: <https://research-portal.uea.ac.uk/en/>

Platforms for popularization of scientific research: n/a

Platforms for digitized historical documentation: East Anglian Film Archive: <https://eafa.org.uk/>

; UEA archive: <https://www.uea.ac.uk/web/library/library-archives-and-collections/archives-a-z>

CBS

Current research information system (CRIS): <https://research.cbs.dk/>

Institutional repository for Open Access publications: <https://research.cbs.dk/>

Institutional repository for doctoral dissertations: <https://research.cbs.dk/>

Platform for the publication of open access scientific journals: <https://rauli.cbs.dk>

Platforms for popularisation of scientific research: <https://www.cbs.dk/> & <https://cbswire.dk/>

Long-term storage

UI

Long-term storage of e-Journals/e-book series: www.rafhladan.is

Long-term storage of Research data: Not available.

Long-term storage of Open educational resources: Not available.

Long-term storage of digitized historic documents: In-house development

VU

Long-term storage of e-Journals/e-book series: -

Long-term storage of Research data: [YoDa](#), [DataverseNL](#)

Long-term storage of Open educational resources: <https://edusources.nl/>

Long-term storage of digitized historic documents: -

UDE

Long-term storage of e-Journals/e-book series: German National Library (<https://portal.dnb.de>)

Long-term storage of Research data: Research data associated with a dissertation are archived for the long term via the German National Library (<https://portal.dnb.de>). The consortium rds.nrw provides long-term storage according to the FAIR data principles for published and unpublished research data.

Long-term storage of Open educational resources: ORCA.nrw (<https://www.orca.nrw>)

Long-term storage of digitized historic documents: Currently publishing and storing via DuEPublico (e.g. <https://duepublico2.uni-due.de/content/mercator>)

URV

Long-term storage of e-Journals/e-book series: <http://repositori.urv.cat>

Long-term storage of Research data: <http://repositori.urv.cat>

Long-term storage of Open educational resources: Not available YET

Long-term storage of digitized historic documents: <http://repositori.urv.cat>

UIBK

Long-term storage of e-Journals/e-book series: Long-term preservation via institutional repository

Long-term storage of Research data: Long-term preservation strategy based on

<https://www.archivematica.org/>

Long-term storage of Open educational resources: Long-term preservation strategy based on

<https://www.archivematica.org/>

Long-term storage of digitized historic documents: Long-term preservation strategy based on

<https://www.archivematica.org/>

UNINA

Long-term storage of e-Journals/e-book series: **depositolegale.it** (<https://www.depositolegale.it/>);

Network LOCKSS (Lots of Copies Keep Stuff Safe) (<https://www.lockss.org/>);

Long-term storage of Research data: **depositolegale.it** (<https://www.depositolegale.it/>)

Long-term storage of Open educational resources: *Not available.*

Long-term storage of digitized historic documents: *Not available.*

UPOL

Long-term storage of e-Journals/e-book series: University Press information system called Actavia

Long-term storage of Research data: there are third party solutions like [Amazon S3 Glacier storage](#) or [CESNET](#) - Czech Education and Scientific NETwork [DataCare](#) offered for that purpose but at the cost of fees.

Long-term storage of Open educational resources: n/a

Long-term storage of digitized historic documents: n/a

UEA

Long-term storage of e-Journals/e-book series: Eprints

Long-term storage of Research data: Pure

Long-term storage of Open educational resources: Pure

Long-term storage of digitized historic documents: UEA Archives

<https://www.uea.ac.uk/web/library/library-archives-and-collections/archives-a-z>

CBS

Long-term storage of e-Journals/e-book series: Not available

Long-term storage of Research data: CBS does not have an institutional data repository. CBS researchers are advised to publish their data on [Zenodo](#) (open & closed datasets), [Harvard Dataverse](#) (open datasets) or [Open Science Framework](#) (open datasets). Denmark will establish a National Data Repository in 2024 based on Dataverse: <https://www.deic.dk/en/node/2147>. This will be used to archive open and closed datasets.

Long-term storage of Open educational resources: Not available

Long-term storage of digitized historic documents: Not available